

Supplementary Information

S.1 Historical Context

Financial interests acted as a principal driver in the adoption of the first zoning ordinance. Business and real estate owners feared that uncontrolled growth would cause economic problems, and they pressured local officials to adopt a zoning ordinance (Weiss, 1992; Toll, 1969; Fischler, 1998). Present-day zoning continues to be used as a tool to promote economic growth, typically through flexible (creation of economic growth zones molded by developers) and incentive zoning (incentivizing developers to build valuable amenities; Sclar, 2019). For example, the Town of Apex, North Carolina (NC) proposed the use of financial and non-financial incentives to develop affordable housing, including an increase in allowable density and grants to offset housing costs (Town of Apex, 2022). Additionally, early zoning proponents touted zoning as a way to protect the largest investment of most Americans, the single-family home, from devaluation caused by the nearby construction of industrial or commercial sites (Fischler, 1998). This historical focus on the creation of residential zones influences present-day land use, as over 50% of urban areas are zoned for single-family residences alone (Hirt, 2015).

Environmental and human health advocates also acted as influential zoning supporters in the early 1920s. Supporters spoke to the benefits of zoning to relocate industrial and commercial sites away from residences, thereby improving the air quality in neighborhoods and reducing the spread of diseases caused by overcrowding (Fischler, 1998). Present-day smart-zoning and rezoning strategies are leveraged to protect people and property against immediate natural hazards (e.g., flooding), reducing the need and cost of rebuilding after a disaster (U.S. EPA,

2017). For example, after Superstorm Sandy, New York City passed a zoning amendment to improve flood resiliency in flood-prone neighborhoods (Watson, 2019).

Zoning has also been used as a powerful (and often negative) tool to shape society. With explicit racial zoning outlawed in 1917, white homeowners turned to zoning ordinances as a means to indirectly segregate areas by restricting lot sizes, limiting the number of multifamily units allowed, and banning renting (Trounstine, 2021; Wilson & Appiah-Opoku, 2011). Additionally, while environmental and human health advocates promised improvements as a result of zoning, segregation and unjust housing practices (e.g., redlining) resulted in communities of color being commonly located near industrial sites and thus exposed to pollutants (Trounstine, 2020; Hirt, 2015). Today, many planners seek to rectify these failures by reimagining zoning to address past harms and more equitably redistribute resources (inclusionary zoning; Cassola, 2019; Schuetz & Meltzer, 2012). For example, a study assessing zoning in Durham, North Carolina (NC) found that a change of city council in the mid-1980s led to a shift from zoning acting as a “tool of discrimination to one that could mitigate the harms of past discrimination” (Whittemore, 2019, p.255).

Table S1. Displays reclassification rules for generalizing zoning districts. (a) Includes district name and keywords used to match observed zoning district to generalized district. (b) All zones classified as “residential” go through secondary reclassification based on size of allowable dwelling units (sq ft).

a

District	Keywords
Open Space	"open space", "open-space", "conservancy", "conservation", "natural resources", "water", "wetland", "flood", "recreation"
Planned Use	"planned"
Downtown	"downtown", "central business*", "main street", "city center"
Mixed-Use	"mixed-use", "mixed use", "mix", "employment center", "all uses", "commerce park", "business park", "corporate park"
Commercial	"commercial", "retail", "business", "shopping", "residential office", "residential-office"
Industrial	"industrial", "manufacturing"
Office	"institution*", "office", "medical", "universit*", "education*"
Residential	"residential", "multifamily", "multi-family", "manufactured home", "single family", "single-family"
Agriculture	"agricultur*", "farm"

b

Residential Density	Min dwelling unit size (ft ²)	Max dwelling unit size (ft ²)
High	0	6999
Medium-High	7000	14999
Medium	15000	29999
Medium-Low	30000	39999
Low	40001	Inf

Table S2. Percentage of collected zones for core zoning districts for each county.

County	Majority Class	Residential	Non-Residential	Mixed Use
Brunswick	Residential	89.36	8.23	2.41
Buncombe	Mixed Use	25.08	3.24	71.68
Cabarrus	Residential	61.34	29.64	9.03
Carteret	Residential	86.41	11.63	1.96
Chatham	Residential	94.71	3.78	1.51
Cherokee	Residential	51.13	46.57	2.30
Chowan	Residential	98.08	1.92	0.00
Cleveland	Residential	93.75	6.08	0.17
Cumberland	Non-Residential	46.34	49.76	3.90
Currituck	Residential	94.27	5.32	0.42
Dare	Residential	65.96	30.23	3.82
Davidson	Residential	95.95	3.79	0.26
Davie	Residential	98.52	1.48	0.00
Durham	Residential	47.17	34.00	18.82
Forsyth	Residential	86.25	12.45	1.30
Gaston	Residential	87.40	10.80	1.79
Guilford	Residential	90.80	8.01	1.19
Harnett	Residential	91.26	8.62	0.13
Haywood	Residential	83.96	9.20	6.85
Henderson	Residential	93.55	5.61	0.84
Iredell	Residential	93.21	5.19	1.60
Johnston	Residential	97.68	1.46	0.87
Lee	Residential	90.81	6.20	2.99
Lincoln	Residential	91.38	5.11	3.52
Mecklenburg	Residential	71.32	22.56	6.12
New Hanover	Residential	62.95	29.90	7.15
Onslow	Residential	72.61	27.39	0.00
Orange	Residential	82.48	3.52	14.00
Pitt	Residential	96.21	3.49	0.30
Randolph	Residential	93.41	4.28	2.31
Rockingham	Residential	97.53	1.00	1.47
Rowan	Residential	95.55	4.33	0.12
Union	Residential	98.50	1.13	0.37
Wake	Residential	76.83	8.58	14.59
Watauga	Residential	58.94	40.64	0.42
Wayne	Residential	74.14	24.94	0.92
Wilkes	Residential	82.12	17.72	0.16
Wilson	Residential	91.91	7.41	0.68
Yadkin	Residential	96.60	3.39	0.01

Table S3. Percentage of collected zones for sub-districts for each county.

County	Majority Class	R H	R MH	R Med	R ML	R Low	Ag	C	I	O	OS	MU	PU	D
Brunswick	R Med	5.65	15.12	67.95	0.00	0.64	0.00	4.54	2.58	0.00	1.11	0.20	2.21	0.00
Buncombe	MU	1.09	16.95	0.66	0.00	6.39	0.00	1.46	0.14	0.64	1.00	71.57	0.00	0.11
Cabarrus	R MH	16.19	25.07	14.71	0.00	3.71	1.66	9.14	17.01	3.49	0.00	3.49	5.29	0.25
Carteret	R Med	1.94	1.79	68.21	0.00	0.00	14.47	4.75	3.18	0.44	3.27	0.00	1.89	0.07
Chatham	R ML	0.06	0.60	0.51	74.50	18.36	0.69	0.40	3.22	0.16	0.00	0.00	1.49	0.02
Cherokee	R MH	0.00	48.66	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.47	38.48	0.00	0.00	8.09	0.00	0.00	2.30
Chowan	Ag	2.49	0.61	3.27	0.07	4.06	87.59	0.45	1.33	0.14	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Cleveland	R Med	1.03	5.46	81.71	0.01	0.00	5.55	1.71	4.26	0.11	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.08
Cumberland	C	4.24	9.41	13.65	2.29	0.56	16.18	45.95	3.44	0.37	0.00	1.37	2.50	0.04
Currituck	Ag	0.00	0.00	2.77	15.85	12.54	63.11	4.31	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.20	0.22	0.00
Dare	R Med	0.00	0.62	65.34	0.00	0.00	0.00	26.42	3.50	0.00	0.30	0.00	3.82	0.00
Davidson	Ag	0.00	0.02	11.02	0.01	0.00	84.89	0.81	2.68	0.29	0.02	0.26	0.00	0.00
Davie	R ML	0.00	0.29	0.00	98.22	0.00	0.02	0.27	1.20	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Durham	R Med	0.49	19.57	27.07	0.03	0.01	0.00	12.62	15.79	5.59	0.00	0.79	18.04	0.00
Forsyth	R MH	0.13	34.37	14.19	13.49	0.00	24.07	2.24	4.74	0.69	4.79	1.26	0.00	0.04
Gaston	R ML	0.15	15.86	1.51	69.65	0.21	0.03	3.73	6.48	0.57	0.03	0.28	1.51	0.00
Guilford	Ag	0.20	6.63	0.53	19.46	0.00	63.98	1.28	4.65	1.34	0.74	0.27	0.81	0.11
Harnett	R ML	0.26	1.73	40.38	48.89	0.00	0.00	1.61	2.38	0.38	4.26	0.04	0.05	0.04
Haywood	R MH	0.00	60.43	23.52	0.00	0.00	0.00	5.70	2.31	1.19	0.00	0.84	0.00	6.01
Henderson	R Low	0.16	11.78	2.54	3.67	75.40	0.00	2.70	1.75	0.57	0.59	0.31	0.50	0.04
Iredell	R Med	0.36	4.01	86.26	2.46	0.11	0.01	1.86	3.17	0.16	0.00	1.28	0.15	0.17
Johnston	R ML	0.00	0.00	0.00	97.68	0.00	0.00	0.17	1.27	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.86	0.00
Lee	R ML	0.00	0.45	6.74	83.58	0.04	0.00	1.13	4.39	0.68	0.00	2.85	0.11	0.03
Lincoln	R ML	0.00	1.10	41.26	49.02	0.00	0.00	2.12	2.71	0.17	0.11	0.02	3.47	0.03
Mecklenburg	R MH	18.66	35.64	16.92	0.00	0.10	0.00	6.29	13.30	1.83	1.15	5.97	0.14	0.01
New Hanover	R Med	2.78	6.63	46.49	0.00	0.91	6.16	4.59	22.49	2.82	0.00	3.00	3.89	0.26

Onslow	Ag	0.85	11.10	8.78	2.57	0.00	49.31	3.25	0.46	0.50	23.17	0.00	0.00	0.00
Orange	R ML	1.02	2.21	4.35	73.85	1.04	0.02	1.05	0.29	1.08	1.11	0.30	13.69	0.00
Pitt	Ag	1.37	1.14	17.81	1.71	0.00	74.18	1.08	1.41	0.99	0.00	0.01	0.30	0.00
Randolph	R ML	0.23	1.13	2.88	87.98	1.17	0.02	0.96	2.23	0.19	0.90	2.29	0.00	0.02
Rockingham	R ML	0.00	0.00	5.31	92.16	0.00	0.06	0.29	0.65	0.07	0.00	1.47	0.00	0.00
Rowan	Ag	0.00	0.06	5.64	0.00	0.39	89.47	2.43	1.90	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.00	0.00
Union	R ML	0.26	0.16	4.34	93.66	0.09	0.00	0.69	0.44	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.37	0.00
Wake	R ML	8.65	16.95	2.95	32.25	15.24	0.79	2.73	3.53	1.31	1.01	7.84	6.36	0.39
Watauga	R MH	1.78	32.47	24.54	0.00	0.14	0.00	25.89	2.04	12.72	0.00	0.27	0.00	0.15
Wayne	R Med	1.91	5.16	54.28	12.08	0.00	0.70	8.20	12.76	3.98	0.00	0.69	0.00	0.23
Wilkes	R Med	4.45	16.05	61.27	0.00	0.00	0.35	11.49	5.79	0.45	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.16
Wilson	R ML	3.97	1.11	1.18	80.01	0.00	5.64	1.56	4.87	0.02	0.95	0.68	0.00	0.00
Yadkin	Ag	0.00	0.05	1.43	1.98	0.00	93.14	1.84	1.27	0.08	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.01

RH = Residential High Density, RMH = Residential Medium-High Density, R med = Residential Medium Density, RML = Residential Medium-Low Density, R Low= Residential Low Density, Ag = Residential Agricultural, C = Commercial, I = Industrial, O = Office, OS = Open Space, MU = Mixed Use, PU = Planned Use, D = Downtown.

S.2 Data availability sensitivity test

To test the robustness of the model and account for differing data availability, we developed sensitivity tests by progressively increasing the proportion of data removed from the training dataset. To do so, we chose three ratios of training and testing splits: 80/20%, 50/50%, 20/80%. We performed tests with each ratio for within and between county tests.

Table S4. Results from all model data availability tests. We systematically removed data from the training dataset to assess how model performance changes with limited data availability. Below shows results from three train/test splits: 80% training and 20% testing, 50% training and 50% testing, and 20% training and 80% testing.

Model	District	Recall			Precision			F1 Score		
Within	Core district	80	50	20	80	50	20	80	50	20
	Residential	0.9849	0.9846	0.9829	0.9981	0.9979	0.9972	0.9915	0.9912	0.99
	Non-Residential	0.9831	0.9807	0.9742	0.8926	0.8903	0.8779	0.9357	0.9333	0.9235
	Mixed Use	0.9926	0.9912	0.9881	0.9535	0.9514	0.9451	0.9727	0.9709	0.9661
	macro average	0.9888	0.9875	0.984	0.9571	0.9557	0.95	0.9723	0.9709	0.9662
	Sub-district									
	Residential High	0.9590	0.9533	0.9379	0.9604	0.9542	0.9392	0.9597	0.9538	0.9385
	Residential Medium-High	0.9666	0.9635	0.9528	0.9818	0.9793	0.9727	0.9741	0.9713	0.9627
	Residential Medium	0.9875	0.9861	0.9823	0.9819	0.9816	0.9777	0.9847	0.9838	0.9800
	Residential Medium-Low	0.9876	0.9871	0.9853	0.9950	0.9947	0.9933	0.9913	0.9909	0.9893
	Residential Low	0.9941	0.9932	0.9904	0.9920	0.9907	0.9888	0.993	0.992	0.9896
	Residential Agriculture	0.9826	0.9827	0.9793	0.9966	0.9962	0.995	0.9895	0.9894	0.9871
	Commercial	0.9753	0.9716	0.9622	0.9359	0.9318	0.9141	0.9552	0.9513	0.9375
	Industrial	0.9784	0.9748	0.966	0.9467	0.9428	0.9277	0.9623	0.9585	0.9464

Office	0.9653	0.9600	0.9435	0.897	0.8864	0.8529	0.9299	0.9217	0.8959	
Open Space	0.9844	0.9829	0.9776	0.9371	0.933	0.9258	0.9602	0.9573	0.951	
Mixed Use	0.9924	0.9912	0.988	0.9771	0.9752	0.9703	0.9847	0.9832	0.9791	
Planned Use	0.9846	0.9816	0.9748	0.9819	0.9792	0.9716	0.9832	0.9804	0.9732	
Downtown	0.9686	0.9624	0.9465	0.9437	0.9312	0.8982	0.9560	0.9465	0.9217	
macro average	0.9792	0.9763	0.968	0.9621	0.9582	0.9462	0.9704	0.967	0.9567	
		Precision			Recall			F1 Score		
Between Core district	80	50	20	80	50	20	80	50	20	
Residential	0.8447	0.8348	0.8107	0.9837	0.9819	0.9941	0.9089	0.9024	0.8930	
Non-Residential	0.6601	0.7944	0.6901	0.0623	0.1014	0.0988	0.1138	0.1799	0.1729	
Mixed Use	0.0026	0.0125	0.0406	0.0040	0.0355	0.0033	0.0032	0.0185	0.0061	
macro average	0.3769	0.4693	0.5846	0.2625	0.2797	0.2741	0.2565	0.2752	0.2681	
Sub-district										
Residential High	0.5760	0.5209	0.6458	0.0143	0.1528	0.0001	0.0280	0.2363	0.0002	
Residential Medium-High	0.3384	0.3830	0.3612	0.0665	0.3869	0.2911	0.1111	0.3849	0.3224	
Residential Medium	0.3839	0.1840	0.1547	0.3110	0.1095	0.2571	0.3436	0.1373	0.1931	
Residential Medium-Low	0.3118	0.2372	0.2625	0.8953	0.9916	0.0789	0.4625	0.3829	0.1213	
Residential Low	0.8774	0.0171	0.0390	0.0307	0.0003	0.3383	0.0593	0.0006	0.0700	

Residential									
Agriculture	0.0181	0.4514	0.2144	0.0124	0.0559	0.3343	0.0147	0.0995	0.2612
Commercial	0.3345	0.4010	0.2809	0.1139	0.0383	0.0567	0.1699	0.0700	0.0944
Industrial	0.4714	0.3329	0.4018	0.0600	0.0893	0.1277	0.1064	0.1409	0.1938
Office	0.7593	0.0264	0.1052	0.0166	0.0037	0.0105	0.0324	0.0065	0.0191
Open Space	0.7662	0.0190	0.1031	0.0625	0.0016	0.0178	0.1156	0.0030	0.0304
Mixed Use	0.0233	0.0309	0.0329	0.0012	0.0039	0.0005	0.0023	0.0069	0.0010
Planned Use	0.0000	0.0004	0.1105	0.0000	0.0001	0.0007	0.0000	0.0001	0.0014
Downtown	0.0000	0.0048	0.1111	0.0000	0.0002	0.0035	0.0000	0.0004	0.0069
macro average	0.3907	0.1717	0.1854	0.1057	0.1149	0.0988	0.0966	0.0924	0.0877

Fig. S1. Between-county sub-district model predictions and performance for two of the 15 random training county samples (e, f; pink boundary lines show counties used for testing). (a) Observed and (b,c) predicted sub-districts from sampling schemes (b) S1 and (c) S2. (d) Proportion of misclassified pixels aggregated to a 3-km grid from samples (e) S1 and (f) S2

S.3 Sensitivity of Sample Size Training Datasets and Landscape Context

We found no clear relationship between data coverage or rural/urban quality and performance.

Cherokee County has the lowest data coverage (less than 1%) but showed lower error than the statewide average for the between-county sub-district model (6.23% compared to statewide mean of 8.58%; Fig. S1; Table S10).

Table S5. Mean percent error (MPE) by county for between-county sub-district and core district models.

County	Type	Data Coverage	MPE - Between-county core	MPE - Between-county sub
Brunswick	Urban	82.05%	2.33%	19.41%
Buncombe	Urban	94.45%	8.69%	19.11%
Cabarrus	Rural	6.39%	8.74%	11.99%
Carteret	Rural	8.35%	2.26%	14.93%
Chatham	Urban	95.59%	0.62%	7.30%
Cherokee	Rural	0.92%	5.46%	6.23%
Chowan	Rural	72.43%	0.14%	13.22%
Cleveland	Rural	91.89%	1.70%	9.92%
Cumberland	Urban	83.16%	11.75%	15.02%
Currituck	Rural	52.12%	1.28%	9.22%
Dare	Rural	3.77%	8.34%	11.32%
Davidson	Urban	88.99%	1.32%	7.37%
Davie	Urban	88.53%	0.30%	7.63%
Durham	Urban	95.09%	5.69%	3.08%
Forsyth	Urban	92.36%	3.10%	5.53%
Gaston	Rural	76.06%	4.02%	5.82%
Guilford	Urban	61.95%	2.77%	13.11%
Harnett	Rural	99.92%	3.53%	5.70%
Haywood	Urban	4.68%	2.17%	7.71%
Henderson	Urban	90.03%	0.81%	6.54%
Iredell	Urban	97.25%	1.85%	18.80%
Johnston	Urban	72.32%	0.67%	7.52%
Lee	Rural	89.55%	1.30%	5.23%
Lincoln	Rural	92.35%	2.53%	10.16%
Mecklenburg	Urban	72.63%	3.04%	5.84%
New Hanover	Urban	79.74%	3.69%	12.11%
Onslow	Urban	49.97%	4.78%	6.65%
Orange	Urban	97.51%	4.72%	11.79%
Pitt	Urban	84.59%	0.90%	3.29%

Randolph	Rural	98.39%	2.21%	4.00%
Rockingham	Rural	72.39%	1.68%	4.33%
Rowan	Rural	78.22%	1.34%	6.85%
Union	Urban	67.76%	0.55%	6.57%
Wake	Urban	74.31%	6.19%	6.29%
Watauga	Rural	1.81%	4.47%	9.99%
Wayne	Urban	46.55%	5.44%	8.05%
Wilkes	Rural	5.61%	2.34%	3.16%
Wilson	Rural	86.12%	2.59%	0.34%
Yadkin	Rural	93.79%	1.82%	3.50%

Fig S2. Mean percent error (MPE) by percent data coverage by county for (a) core district between-county and (b) sub-district between-county models. Colorized by urban/rural characteristics (black circle for urban, gray triangle for rural).

Supplementary References

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